

Some Halogenated Sulphonamides with Biological Interest

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Various types of sulphonamides derived from 2,5-dichloro- or 2,5-dibromobenzene-sulphonyl chlorides are prepared. Among these are the pyrazoline (IVa-d and X), the isoxazoline (IVe) and the thioxopyrimidine derivatives (Va, b and XI). Secondary amines as thiols add on the sulphonamides (IIa, b) to give (VIa-d and VIIa, b), respectively. Active methylene compounds react with the sulphonamides (IIa, b and III) to give the cyclohexenone derivatives (IXa-d and XIIa, b), respectively. H_2O_2 on reaction with IIb gives a sulphonamide containing α,β -epoxyketone (XV) which react with hydrazines, acetic acid and piperidine to give XVI, XVIIa and XVIIb, respectively. The biological activity of the products against different organisms are discussed.

In continuation of our work on 2,5-dichloro-benzenesulphonyl chloride and related compounds¹, some new sulphonamides containing heterocyclic rings have been prepared and their biological activities have been studied.

Thus, interaction of 2,5-dichloro²- or 2,5-dibromo³-benzenesulphonyl chloride with *p*-aminoacetophenone gave the sulphonamides Ia¹ and Ib, respectively. Interaction of Ia, b with aldehydes gave the corresponding chalcones (IIa-c). From the reaction of Ia with benzaldehyde, two products could be isolated, one of them was analysed for the expected chalcone (IIa) while the other was analysed for (III).

I
Ia; X=Cl
b; X=Br

II
IIa; R=C₆H₅; X=Cl
b; R=C₆H₅; X=Br
c; R=C₆H₄.Cl-o; X=Br

III

The structure III was further demonstrated when the experiment was repeated under identical conditions without using benzaldehyde. The product may be a result of aldol condensation.

Condensation of II with hydrazines gave the corresponding pyrazoline derivatives (IVa-c) based on elemental analyses; ν_{max} 3250 (NH), 3100 (SO₂NH) and 1640 cm⁻¹ (C=N); and analogous work⁴. Acetylation of IVa gave IVd, whose ir

spectra showed the absence of NH and the presence of 3140 (SO₂NH) and 1650 cm⁻¹ (NCO).

IV

R	X	Z
IVa; C ₆ H ₅	Cl	NH
b; C ₆ H ₄ .Cl-o	Br	NH
c; C ₆ H ₄ .Cl-o	Br	NO ₂ H ₃
d; C ₆ H ₅	Cl	N.CO.OH ₃
e; C ₆ H ₅	Cl	O

Similarly, interaction of IIa with hydroxylamine hydrochloride gave the isoxazoline derivative (IVe) on the basis of elemental analyses and ir spectra.

On the other hand, condensation of IIa, b with thiourea afforded the tetrahydrothioxopyrimidine⁶ derivatives (Va, b), ν_{max} 3300 (NH), 3150 (SO₂NH) and 1640 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

V

Va; R=C ₆ H ₅	X=Cl
b; R=C ₆ H ₄ .Cl-o	X=Br

Interaction of IIa, b with secondary amines furnished an addition product⁶ which gave analytical figures compatible with VIa-d. Also addition products⁷ of type VIIa, b were obtained on treating IIa with thiols in presence of piperidine; ν_{max} 750 cm⁻¹ (C-S-N).

- VIa** ; R = C₆H₅ ; R' = piperidyl ; X = Cl
b ; R = C₆H₅ ; R' = morphyl ; X = Cl
c ; R = C₆H₄.Cl-o ; R' = piperidyl ; X = Br
d ; R = C₆H₄.Cl-o ; R' = morphyl ; X = Br
VIIa ; R = C₆H₅ ; R' = S-C₆H₅ ; X = Cl
b ; R = C₆H₅ ; R' = benzothiazolyl ; X = Cl

Bromination of **IIa** gave **VIIIa** which reacted with morpholine to give **VIIIb** based on elemental analyses, ir spectra and previous work⁹.

- VIIIa** ; R = Br
b ; R =
- | | | | |
|------------|-------------------------------------|----------------------------------|----|
| | R | R' | X |
| IXa | O ₆ H ₅ | COOH ₂ | Cl |
| b | O ₆ H ₅ | COOC ₂ H ₅ | Cl |
| c | O ₆ H ₄ .Cl-o | COCH ₃ | Br |
| d | O ₆ H ₄ .Cl-o | COOC ₂ H ₅ | Br |

Condensation of **IIa, b** with active methylene compounds was also successful and the cyclohexenone derivatives of type **IX** were obtained. The structure of these was established by elemental analyses and ir spectra which showed the α,β -unsaturated ketone (1670 cm⁻¹).

Similarly, interaction of **III** with hydrazine hydrate, thiourea, active methylene compounds, bromine and thiophenol are also discussed.

Thus, interaction of **III** with hydrazine hydrate, thiourea or active methylene compounds furnished the corresponding pyrazoline (**X**), tetrahydrothioxopyrimidine (**XI**) or cyclohexenone (**XIIa, b**) derivatives, respectively.

X

XI

XII

- XIIa** ; R = CO₂CH₃
b ; R = COOC₂H₅

Also, interaction of **III** with bromine as well as thiophenol gave the addition products **XIII** and **XIV**, respectively.

- XIII** ; R = R' = Br
XIV ; R = H ; R' = S-C₆H₅

The structures of **X-XIV** were supported by elemental analyses, ir spectra and the above work.

Recently it has been shown that H₂O₂ reacts with α,β -unsaturated ketones to give α,β -epoxy ketones⁹. This reaction has now been applied on the chalcone (**IIb**) which gave a sulphonamide containing α,β -epoxy ketone (**XV**), based on elemental analyses and ir spectra [1700 (CO) and 1260-1240 cm⁻¹ (epoxy linkage)].

XV

XVI

- XVla** ; R = H
b ; R = C₆H₅

The oxirane ring in **XV** was readily opened when **XV** reacted with hydrazines in boiling alcohol to give 4-hydroxypyrazoline derivatives (**XVla, b**), based on elemental analyses, ir spectra [3400 (OH), 3200 (NH), 3100 (SO₂NH) and 1660 cm⁻¹ (C=N)] and previous work¹⁰.

Interaction of the chalcone epoxide (**XV**) with glacial acetic acid affected fission of the oxirane ring¹¹ to give the glycol monoacetate (**XVIIa**). Its ir spectrum showed 3450 (OH) and 1720 and 1680 cm⁻¹ (two C=O groups).

XVII

- XVIIa** ; R = O.CO.OH₂

Similarly, interaction of **XV** with piperidine gave **XVIIb**; ν_{max} [3400 (OH), 3100 (SO₂NH) and 1680 cm⁻¹ (CO)].

Interaction of the sulphonamide (**IIa**) with ethyl formate and ethyl acetate furnished **XVIIIa** and **b** respectively; the structure was confirmed by elemental analyses and ir spectra [3150 (SO₂NH), 1700 cm⁻¹ (CO double peak)].

- XVIIIa ; Z=H₂ ; R=H
 b ; Z=H₂ ; R=CH₃
 XIXa ; Z=N.NH.C₆H₅ ; R=CH₃
 b ; Z=N.NH.C₆H₄.CH₃-o ; R=CH₃

Interaction of XVIIIb with aryldiazonium chloride in presence of sodium acetate gave the azo derivatives (XIX a, b), based on elemental analyses and ir spectra.

2,5-Dibromobenzenesulphonyl hydrazide (XXa) was obtained by interaction of the sulphonyl chloride with hydrazine hydrate in alcohol. XXa was reacted with aldehydes, ketones, sulphonyl chlorides and acetyl chloride to give XXb-m.

XX

- XXa, R=NH₂
 b, R=N : CHC₆H₄.OH-p
 c, R=N : CHC₆H₄.NO₂-o
 d, R=N : CHC₆H₄.NO₂-m
 e, R=N : CHC₆H₄.NO₂-p
 f, R=N : CHC₆H₄.Cl-o
 XXg, R=N : CHC₆H₄.N(CH₃)₂-p
 h, R=N : CH.OH : CH.C₆H₅
 i, R=N : O(C₆H₅)₂
 j, R=N : C(CH₃)₂(C₆H₅)
 k, R=NH.O₂S.C₆H₅
 l, R=NH.O₂S.C₆H₄.CH₃-p
 m, R=NH.CO₂H₃

Interaction of XXa with nitrous acid in acid medium^{1,2} gave the corresponding azide (XXIa) ; its ir spectra showed a peak at 2140 cm⁻¹ (SO₂N₃).

XXI

XXIa ; R=N₃

b ; R=N

Interaction of XXIa with piperidine furnished the sulphonamide (XXIb) which was obtained from interaction of 2,5-dibromobenzenesulphonyl chloride with piperidine.

The physical data of the compounds prepared are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Biological activity : Results of the biological activities in terms of MIC ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) of all the 48 compounds are recorded in Table 3. The following organisms were used for the test purpose : *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATTC-6-10145), *Bacillus megaterium* (IMRU-10), *Micrococcus lutea* (IMRU-14), *Candida utilis* (NRL-900), *Mycobacterium smegmatis* (IMRU-24), *Aspergillus niger* (pp 29).

In general, the toxicity of almost all the compounds are very weak against the tested organisms. Out of the 46 compounds, only 15 inhibited the growth of one or more test organism whereas the other 31 did not show any activity.

The biologically active 15 compounds could be classified into 9 groups.

Group 1 : (Va, XXI, XXIc), inhibitory to all the test organisms.

Group 2 : (IVa, VIa, VIIb, VIIIa), inhibitory to all the test organisms except *A. niger*.

Group 3 : (XXa), inhibitory to all the test organisms except *P. aeruginosa*.

Group 4 : (XIII), inhibitory to both the gram positive and acid fast bacteria, and *A. niger*.

Group 5 : (XXi), inhibitory to both gram positive and acid fast bacteria.

Group 6 : (IVb, XVIa), inhibitory to *M. lutea*.

Group 7 : (XXm), inhibitory to *B. megaterium*.

Group 8 : (XIb), inhibitory to gram positive bacteria.

Group 9 : (VIId), inhibitory to *A. niger*.

The fact that the 7 compounds under group 1 and 2, are of high significance from the chemotherapeutic point of view, since many synthetic products exhibiting activities against gram negative bacteria are recorded to have antitumor activity^{13,14}. Further, VIId (group 9) has specific antifungal activity. This behaviour has a special importance in the field of clinical mycology¹⁵.

Interestingly, there are 31 chemical compounds with no activity against all the tested organisms. Most of the compounds exhibited stimulatory effect to promote the growth of most of the tested organisms. This has particular significance in the field of improving the immune system of many patients suffering from drug treatments. Some synthetic polyanions are known to have the ability to induce the production of interferon in man and animals to increase the immune response¹⁶ and also inhibit the growth of murine tumors, particularly solid tumors¹⁷⁻¹⁹. Some investigators find hope in fortifying the natural immune responses as a weapon against malignant tumors²⁰.

However, it is felt that the present data concerning the biological activities of all the 46 tested compounds need further elaboration with special stress on their possible application in chemotherapy and immunotherapy.

Biological assay : This was carried out according to the reported method²¹. The minimum inhibiting concentration (MIC) was determined by the dilution assay technique²². Assay plates were incubated at 28°, 2 days for yeast and fungi, and at 37°, 1 day for bacteria.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra in KBr were recorded on a Beckman IR spectrophotometer.

The sulphonamides Ib and XXIb: These were prepared following the previous method¹.

Condensation of Ia, b with aldehydes: A mixture of I (0.02 mol), the requisite aldehyde (0.02 mol) and piperidine (0.1 ml) in *n*-butanol (50 ml) was heated under reflux for 6 h. The product was

recrystallized to give IIa-c. In case of IIa, the insoluble part was recrystallized from acetic acid to give III.

Pyrazoline (IVa-c and X) and tetrahydrothiopyrimidine (Va, b and XI) derivatives (Table 1): They were prepared as per reported methods^{4,5}.

Acetylation of IVa: A solution of IVa (0.01 mol) in acetic acid (20 ml) was treated with acetyl chloride (0.02 mol) and heated under reflux for 1 h. The product on dilution with water gave IVd.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE SULPHONAMIDE DERIVATIVES (Ib-XI)

Compd. no.	Yield %	Solvent of crystn.	m p. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)*	
					N	S
Ib	85	M	180-83	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ Br ₂ NO ₂ S	3.11 (3.28)	7.42 (7.39)
IIa	63	M	210-12	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ NO ₂ S	3.33 (3.24)	7.53 (7.41)
b	78	E	200	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ Br ₂ NO ₂ S	2.73 (2.69)	6.25 (6.14)
c	76	E	215	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ Br ₂ ClNO ₂ S	2.43 (2.52)	5.79 (5.76)
III	35	A	220-2	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	4.23 (4.18)	9.62 (9.55)
IVa	69	E	130	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.53 (9.41)	7.01 (7.17)
b	67	E	120-1	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ Br ₂ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	7.45 (7.38)	5.78 (5.62)
c	70	E	140	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ Br ₂ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	6.59 (6.51)	5.01 (4.96)
d	68	E	240	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.72 (8.61)	6.52 (6.65)
e	65	E	152-5	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	6.18 (6.26)	7.03 (7.16)
Va	78	E	130-2	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	8.83 (8.79)	13.52 (13.39)
b	77	E	240-3	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ ClBr ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	7.04 (6.98)	10.73 (10.65)
VIa	68	E	172	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	5.52 (5.41)	6.33 (6.19)
b	66	E	215	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	5.40 (5.39)	6.15 (6.17)
c	69	P	210	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ Br ₂ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	4.45 (4.37)	5.12 (5.00)
d	65	E	200	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ Br ₂ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	4.48 (4.37)	4.82 (4.98)
VIIa	75	E	168	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ NO ₂ S ₂	2.63 (2.59)	11.72 (11.83)
b	72	E	177-8	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	4.58 (4.68)	16.12 (16.05)
VIIIa	58	E	185	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ Br ₂ NO ₂ S	2.48 (2.37)	5.32 (5.41)
b	60	E	175	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	6.90 (6.95)	5.25 (5.30)
IXa	71	E	90	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ NO ₂ S	2.79 (2.73)	6.32 (6.24)
b	74	E	190-3	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ Cl ₂ NO ₂ S	2.65 (2.59)	5.82 (5.89)
c	75	E	130-2	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ ClBr ₂ NO ₂ S	2.25 (2.20)	5.12 (5.03)
d	70	E	220	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ ClBr ₂ NO ₂ S	2.05 (2.10)	4.85 (4.80)
X	66	E	179	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	8.30 (8.19)	9.45 (9.36)
XI	64	E	260	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	7.82 (7.69)	13.09 (13.19)

A = Acetic acid, E = Ethanol, M = Methanol, P = Petroleum ether (60-80°)

* All the compounds gave satisfactory C and H analysis.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE SULPHONAMIDE DERIVATIVES (XII-XXI)

Compd. no.	Yield %	Solvent of crystn.	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis ; Found/(Calcd.)*	
					N	S
XIIa	66	E	228-5	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	3.71 (3.73)	8.54 (8.52)
b	68	E	230	C ₂₄ H ₂₇ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	3.60 (3.59)	8.22 (8.19)
XIII	76	E	181-3	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ Br ₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	3.34 (3.37)	7.52 (7.71)
XIV	75	E	60	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	3.62 (3.83)	13.08 (13.11)
XV	73	E	95	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ Br ₂ ClNO ₂ S	2.50 (2.45)	5.70 (5.60)
XVIa	68	E	215	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ Br ₂ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	7.22 (7.19)	5.50 (5.47)
b	64	E	112-5	C ₂₇ H ₁₉ Br ₂ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	6.40 (6.36)	4.80 (4.84)
XVIIa	78	E	185	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ Br ₂ ClNO ₂ S	2.32 (2.21)	5.12 (5.07)
b	76	E	128	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ Br ₂ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	4.21 (4.27)	4.71 (4.87)
XVIIIa	75	E	209-12	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ NO ₂ S	3.82 (3.76)	8.61 (8.60)
b	76	E	168	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ NO ₂ S	3.71 (3.68)	8.42 (8.80)
XIXa	78	E	120-3	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.62 (8.57)	6.48 (6.58)
b	70	E	135	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.42 (8.38)	6.41 (6.35)
XXa	82	E	170-3	C ₈ H ₆ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.52 (8.48)	9.81 (9.70)
b	83	E	215	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	6.32 (6.45)	7.45 (7.37)
c	80	E	110	C ₁₃ H ₉ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.52 (9.67)	6.98 (6.91)
d	81	E	150	C ₁₃ H ₉ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.72 (9.67)	7.00 (6.91)
e	79	E	240	C ₁₃ H ₉ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.61 (9.67)	6.83 (6.91)
f	80	E	125	C ₁₃ H ₉ Br ₂ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	6.01 (6.19)	7.00 (7.07)
g	78	E	225	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.15 (9.11)	7.01 (6.94)
h	81	E	150	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	5.82 (5.95)	6.92 (6.84)
i	83	E	160	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	5.53 (5.67)	6.31 (6.48)
j	85	E	180	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	6.48 (6.48)	7.59 (7.41)
k	84	E	185	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	6.01 (5.96)	13.72 (13.62)
l	78	E	170	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	5.92 (5.79)	13.29 (13.22)
m	76	E	120	C ₈ H ₆ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	7.59 (7.53)	8.68 (8.60)
XXIa	66	P	170	C ₈ H ₆ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.20 (12.32)	9.51 (9.38)
b	68	E	95	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ Br ₂ NO ₂	3.52 (3.66)	8.22 (8.36)

E = Ethanol, P = Petroleum ether (60-80°)

* All the compounds gave satisfactory C and H analysis.

Interaction of IIa with H₂N.OH.HCl : A mixture of IIa (0.01 mol) and H₂NOH.HCl (0.01 mol) in pyridine (50 ml) was heated under reflux for 6 h to give IVe.

Interaction of IIa, b with secondary amines : A mixture of II (0.01 mol) and piperidine or morpholine (0.01 mol) in dry benzene (50 ml) was

heated under reflux for 0.5 h, then allowed to stand at room temp overnight, and light petroleum ether (40-60°) was added to give VIa-d. Compounds VIIa, b and XIV were prepared similarly as described earlier⁷.

Bromination of IIa and III : A solution of IIa or III (0.01 mol) in acetic acid (20 ml) was treated

TABLE 3—MINIMUM INHIBITING CONCENTRATIONS (MIC) ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) FOR THE 49 COMPOUNDS TESTED AGAINST ORGANISMS

Compd. No.	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>B. megaterium</i>	<i>M. lutea</i>	<i>C. utilis</i>	<i>M. smegmatis</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
IIa	—	—	—	—	—	—
III	—	—	—	—	—	—
IVa	75	37.5	15	37.5	15	—
IVb	—	—	62	—	—	—
IVd	—	—	—	—	—	—
IVe	—	—	—	—	—	—
Va	40	20	20	20	20	20
Vb	—	—	—	—	—	—
VIa	120	60	24	120	24	—
VIb	—	—	—	—	—	—
VIc	—	—	—	—	—	—
VId	—	—	—	—	—	181
VIIa	—	—	—	—	—	—
VIIb	140	140	140	140	140	—
VIIIa	190	190	190	190	190	—
VIIIb	—	—	—	—	—	—
IXa	—	—	—	—	—	—
IXb	—	—	—	—	—	—
IXc	—	—	—	—	—	—
Xa	—	—	—	—	—	—
Xb	—	—	—	—	—	—
XI	—	—	—	—	—	—
XIIa	—	—	—	—	—	—
XIIb	—	16	80	—	—	—
XIII	—	24.4	24.4	—	24.4	122
XIV	—	—	—	—	—	—
XVIa	—	—	65.5	—	—	—
XVIIa	—	—	—	—	—	—
XVIIb	—	—	—	—	—	—
XVIIc	—	—	—	—	—	—
XVIIIa	—	—	—	—	—	—
XIXa	—	—	—	—	—	—
XIXb	—	—	—	—	—	—
XXa	(—)	220	110	220	110	220
XXb	—	—	—	—	—	—
XXc	—	—	—	—	—	—
XXd	—	—	—	—	—	—
XXe	—	—	—	—	—	—
XXf	—	—	—	—	—	—
XXg	—	—	—	—	—	—
XXh	—	—	—	—	—	—
XXi	—	65	65	—	130	—
XXl	500	500	254	500	254	500
XXm	—	156	—	—	—	—
XXIa	456	456	228	456	228	456
XXIb	—	—	—	—	—	—

(—) No activity.

with bromine (0.01 mol) in acetic acid (20 ml) and then concentrated to give VIIIa or XIII.

Interaction of VIIIa with morpholine: A solution of VIIIa (0.01 mol) in methanol (50 ml) and morpholine (0.02 mol) was heated under reflux for 0.5 h and allowed to stand over night at room temp. Dilute acetic acid was added to give VIIIb.

Interaction of IIa, b or III with active methylene compounds: A mixture of IIa, b or III (0.01 mol), active methylene compound (0.01 mol) and piperidine (0.5 ml) in *n*-butanol (50 ml) was heated under reflux for 8 h. Dilute HCl was added to give IXa-d or XIIa, b.

α,β -Epoxy ketone (XV) and 4-hydroxypyrazoline (XVIa, b) derivatives: These were prepared following the reported methods^{9,10}.

Interaction of the epoxide (XV) with glacial acetic acid: A mixture of XV (2 g) and acetic acid (10 ml) was left at room temp for 24 h, then diluted with water to give XVIIa.

Interaction of XV with piperidine: A solution of XV (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) and piperidine (0.02 ml) was heated under reflux for 4 h. The product on concentration and cooling gave XVIIb.

Formation of XVIIIa, b: A solution of Ia (0.01 mol) in ethylformate or ethylacetate (50 ml) was slowly added to powdered sodium metal (4 g) and heated under reflux for 5 h; then cooled, treated with a few drops of methanol and water (300 ml) and finally extracted with ether. The aqueous layer was acidified with acetic acid to give XVIIIa,b.

Coupling of XVIIIb with diazonium salts: Diazotized aniline or *o*-toluidine (0.01 mol) was added with stirring to a cold solution of XVIIIb (0.01 mol) in aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (2.5%, 50 ml). Sodium acetate (2 g) was then added and the reaction mixture was left overnight to give XIXa, b.

Formation of XXa: A solution of Ib (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) was stirred at room temp for 0.5 h to give XXa.

Interaction of XXa with aldehydes, ketones, sulphonyl chloride and acetyl chloride: A mixture of XXa (0.01 mol) and the appropriate aldehyde, ketone, sulphonyl chloride or acetyl chloride (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was heated under reflux for 1 h to give XXb-h, XXI, j, XXk, l and XXm.

Azide derivative (XXIa): It was prepared following the reported method¹².

Interaction of XXIa with piperidine: The azide XXIa (1 g) in piperidine (20 ml) was heated under reflux for 6 h and then evaporated under vacuum to give XXfb.

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